

Optimized shelf uprights through the use of high-strength steels

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ABSTRACT

Expanding online trade and limited space capacity characterize warehouse technology worldwide. Despite these increased requirements, the technical design of racking structures has hardly changed. The potential of modern high-strength steel is not fully exploited in modern warehouse technology, due to the lack of scientific studies, although thin-walled cold-formed sections, in particular rack uprights, are predestined for the use of high-strength steel. The research project presented in this paper dealt with the development of manufacturing and design fundamentals for the use of high-strength steel in shelving. For this purpose, the properties of various complex-phase steels, dual-phase steels and high-strength structural steels were first tested with regard to their material and forming behavior. Demonstrator uprights were then manufactured from best suitable high-strength steel. The cross-sectional thickness of the demonstrator uprights made of high-strength steels was reduced in such a way that comparable load-bearing capacities could be achieved with similar components made from steels currently used on the market. To analyse the highly complex stability behavior of thin-walled cold-formed steel sections, the demonstrator uprights were investigated in compression tests with regard to the load-bearing capacity, the governing failure modes and the utilization of the high-strength steel. In addition, numerical parameter studies were used to further optimize the cross-sections for the use of high-strength steel. It could be shown that by using high-strength steel material saving and thus sustainable and economical cross-sections of the rack uprights in shelving can be achieved.

Keywords: High-strength steel, cold-formed structures, stability, shelving

1 INTRODUCTION

Logistics, warehousing and conveyor technology are becoming increasingly important, particularly due to the growth of online trade. In order to meet the increasing demands of the global economy, taking into account the limited space capacity and to be able to exploit the entire market potential, further developments and optimizations of racking systems are required. Increasingly, high-bay warehouses with heights of up to 50 m or big shelving racks are being realized as walk-in multi-level systems (*Fig. 1*).

Steel is mainly used in racking and shelving. Due to the high material strength, thin-walled component geometries can be achieved, resulting in a minimal weight of the shelving systems and a small footprint.

Uprights and beams in racking and shelving are usually manufactured by roll forming galvanized steel sheets. By punching continuous perforations in uprights and using simple connections (e.g. hooked), the shelves are easy to assemble and the compartment heights can be flexibly adapted to

the customer's requirements. Due to the thin-walled sheets, joining techniques such as hooking and clinching is used, which are not used in conventional steel construction.

Fig. 1. Multi-level shelving (Source: META Regalbau GmbH & Co.KG)

While high-strength steels are already established in the automotive industry, the individual components of rack structures are traditionally manufactured from hot-dip coated steels suitable for cold forming up to S350GD in accordance with EN 10346. Efforts have already been made to establish the use of high-strength steel such as HX460LAD and HX500LAD in high-bay racking systems [1]. However, the research in [1] showed that there is still considerable potential for optimization. This was the starting point of a new research project [2], which dealt with the use of high-strength steel in shelving. This paper reports on the selection of suitable high-strength steels for shelf uprights, the production of demonstrator components made of high-strength steels on which compression tests were carried out. FE-analyses are used to optimize the cross-section geometries for optimum utilization of the high material strength.

2 MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

For a preselection of suitable high-strength steels for the production of cold-formed shelving components, various steels were examined in [2] with regard to the production requirements. Fig. 2 provides an overview of different types of high-strength steel used in mechanical engineering or automotive in relation to their tensile strength and elongation at rupture. Three dual-phase steels (DP780, DP980, DP1180), one complex-phase steel (CP980) and one high-strength structural steel (S550GD) were selected for the investigations, as these are characterized by both good deformation properties and high material strength. Table 1 provides an overview of the material, the sheet thicknesses investigated and the material properties. The sheet thicknesses were based on the dimensions that are common for shelf uprights.

Fig. 2. Comparison of the strengths of the steel materials acc. to [3]

In the next step, three bending processes shown in Fig. 3 were carried out with the selected materials from Table 1. These are free bending at a 90° angle (tool radius 2 mm) with clamping on one side, free bending at a 90° angle (tool radius 2 mm) and folding through 180° without an

intermediate layer. The selected high-strength steels proved to be suitable for bending without cracking. Only the test specimens made of DP1180 failed in the bending tests. Afterwards, the test specimens were evaluated with regard to cracking and springback.

Table 1. Tested materials with sheet thicknesses and material properties (nominal values)

Steel grade	Thickness [mm]	R_e [N/mm ²]	R_m [N/mm ²]	A_{80} [%]
DP780	1.2	440-550	780-900	18
	1.5			
DP980	1.2	700-850	980-1130	12
	1.5			
DP1180	1.5	855-960	1120-1270	10
CP980	1.2	780-950	980-1140	6
	1.5			
S550GD	1.25	550	590-770	16
	1.5			

Fig. 3. a) Free bending through 90° with clamping on one side b) Free bending through 90° without wall contact c) Folding through 180° without intermediate layer, acc. to DIN EN ISO 7438

The next step was to carry out punching tests. In addition to the assessment of edge cracking, burr formation and influences on the surface, the required punching force is an important criterion for the selection of materials. A punching tool for a slotted hole (8.0x16 mm) was used in the investigations. Exemplarily, the results of the punching test on a specimen made of S550GD with a thickness of 1.2 mm are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Punching tests on S550GD, sheet: $t=1.2$ mm a) Upper side of the punched sheet b) Sectional view left c) Sectional view right

Overall, the punching tests showed no material-related restrictions for this production process. There was no spalling of the zinc layer, only slight burr formation was detected and no cracks appeared at the punched holes. As was to be expected, the required punching force increased with increasing material strength and sheet thickness. This leads to a shorter tool life and must therefore be taken into account when selecting high-strength materials.

In a further step, the suitability of the high-strength steels with regard to clinching was investigated. Clinch points are particularly important when closing the shelf components, see Fig. 5 a). The

process steps for creating a clinch point using the round point method are shown in Fig. 5 b). For each high-strength material, five clinch connections were made using the round point method, the resulting undercuts were assessed on cross-section specimens and shear tensile tests were carried out in order to assess the load-bearing capacity. It was shown that clinching cannot be used reliably with material DP1180. All other specimens provided stable, reproducible clinch connections.

Fig. 5. a) Clinch points on the underside of the shelf b) Process stages in clinching with the round point method acc. to BTM Blechverbindungstechnik GmbH

The overall assessment of the materials with regard to their suitability for the manufacture of shelf components is shown in Table 2.

The initial material characterization showed that ductility tends to decrease with increasing strength. The bending and folding tests showed that DP1180 and CP980 in a thickness of 1.5 mm are not suitable for cold-forming production operations. Punching was not a problem with any of the materials. Only when using DP1180 cracking occurred during clinching.

Table 2. Overall assessment of the material selection

Steel grade and thickness [mm]	Material properties		Bending and folding				Punching	Clinching		Conclusion
	Tensile strength	Elongation at rupture	90° free cracking	90° clamped on one side cracking	180° cracking	Spring-back	Burr formation	Load capacity	Cracking	
DP780 1.2	+	+	++	++	+	o	no	+	+	+
DP780 1.5	+	+	++	++	+	o	no	+	+	+
DP980 1.2	++	+	++	++	+	o	no	+	+	+
DP980 1.5	++	+	++	++	+	o	no	++	+	-
DP1180 1.5	++	-	++	++	-	o	no	++	-	-
CP980 1.2	++	+	++	++	+	o	no	+	+	+
CP980 1.5	++	+	++	++	+	o	no	++	+	-
S550 1.25	+	+	++	++	+	o	no	+	+	+
S550 1.5	+	+	++	++	+	o	no	+	+	+

Note: ++ best suitable; + suitable, o acceptable; - not suitable

3 MATERIAL SELECTION AND PRODUCTION OF THE DEMONSTRATOR SHELF UPRIGHTS

In consultation with the shelf manufacturers, two high-strength materials were initially selected for the production of typical T-shaped shelf uprights made of high-strength steel for further compression tests. Table 3 provides an overview of the selected steels and the actual material properties resulting from tensile tests acc. to EN ISO 6892-1. As the subsequent compression tests on the demonstrator components are to be carried out in comparison with uprights made of conventional steel, the material properties of the standard uprights (S320GD, S350GD) can also be taken from Table 3.

The geometry of the shelf uprights can be seen in *Fig. 6*. The production was carried out without any problems and without adapting the existing forming lines of the shelf manufacturers involved in the research project [2].

Table 3. Selected materials for the test specimens and material properties

Steel grade	Thickness [mm]	$R_{e,min}$ [N/mm ²]	R_e [N/mm ²]	R_m [N/mm ²]	E [N/mm ²]	
S550GD	1.25	550	559.2	610.2	193,540	High-strength steel
DP780	1.0	440	553.5	860.8	181,638	
S350GD	1.5	350	373.0	426.2	188,880	Structural steel for comparison
S320GD	1.25	320	393.3	530.7	185,407	

Fig. 6. a) T-shaped shelf upright in different views b) Demonstrator after production

4 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS INTO THE LOAD-BEARING CAPACITY OF COLD-FORMED SHELF UPRIGHTS

In order to assess the suitability of high-strength steels for use in shelf uprights, compression tests acc. to FEM 10.2.06-2 [4] were carried out on test specimens made of the steel materials summarized in *Table 3* with the geometry shown in *Fig. 6*.

The thin-walled cold-formed T-shaped shelf uprights are at risk of local, distortional and global stability phenomena when subjected to compressive stress. *Fig. 7* shows the different stability modes. Local buckling (i) is characterized by a deflection of flat plates perpendicular to the plate axis. Distortional buckling (ii-iii) is characterized by buckling of the outstand lips, which leads to opening or closing of the section. Global stability modes such as flexural torsional buckling (iv) can also occur in compressed mono-symmetrical sections.

In order to investigate the load-bearing behavior of the demonstrator uprights with regard to various stability modes, compression tests were carried out on uprights of two different lengths. Short specimens ($L=195$ mm) were used to investigate the interaction of local buckling and distortional buckling. The additional influence of global stability modes was examined for specimens with a longer length ($L=645$ mm).

The test set-up in *Fig. 8* a) was based on the specifications of FEM 10.2.06-2, A10.1 [4]. The ends of the specimens were inserted into cross-section-related grooved cap plates that were bolted to connecting plates. Axial spherical plain bearings were fixed to the connecting plates to generate a simple support according to Euler buckling mode 2. The tests were carried out at TU Dortmund University in a testing machine with a maximum force of 600 kN.

The geometry and imperfections of the specimens were measured before testing. The webs of the specimens were scanned with a displacement transducer in order to record the maximum imperfection corresponding to local buckling w_0 at the web. In addition, the thickness t , the opening dimension c and the global precurvatures a and b were recorded in accordance to Fig. 8 b).

Fig. 7. Signature curve of the T-shaped section in compression determined with CUFSM [5]

Fig. 8. a) Test set-up of compression tests on T-shaped shelf uprights b) Measurement of imperfections

Each test series was carried out with the compressive load applied in different eccentricities to the center of gravity of the net cross-section in order to determine the position of the center of gravity of the effective cross-section resulting from local and distortional buckling. For ease of comparison, only the test results where the load was applied to the center of gravity of the net cross-section are listed in Table 4. The test results from the shelf uprights made of high-strength steel DP780 ($R_{e,min}=440 \text{ N/mm}^2$) and S550GD ($R_{e,min}=550 \text{ N/mm}^2$) as well as from the two reference uprights made of conventional steel S320GD ($R_{e,min}=320 \text{ N/mm}^2$) and S350GD ($R_{e,min}=350 \text{ N/mm}^2$) are summarized. In the majority of the tests, instabilities occurred due to local buckling of the web and distortional buckling of the lips, as shown in Fig. 9 b).

A comparison of the load-bearing capacities achieved in the tests (Fig. 9 a) shows shelf uprights with low plate thicknesses made of high-strength steels achieve almost the same load-bearing capacity as uprights made of the steels currently in use, especially for the short uprights. On the one hand, it was proved that material savings are therefore possible by using high-strength steels. On the other hand, a comparison of the utilization of the load-bearing capacity related to the net cross-section $N_{pl,net}$ shows that the high-steel strength cannot always be utilized due to the higher risk of stability. This shows that high-strength steel can be very useful in order to effectively save material. However, due to the high risk of stability, there is a need for optimization of the cross-sections in order to be able to exploit the high material strength. In particular, two areas of the cross-section were found to be particularly at risk in terms of stability: (1) the web in case of local buckling; (2) the open edge areas for distortional buckling.

Table 4. Results of compression tests on T-shaped uprights with load application in the center of gravity of the net cross-section

Name of test series	Material	Quantity	L [mm]	Section values ¹⁾			Imperfections ^{1),2)}					Bearing load [kN]	Stability mode ³⁾
				t [mm]	A_{net} [mm ²]	I_y [mm ⁴]	w_0 [mm]	c_{max} [mm]	c_0 [mm]	L/a	L/b		
T_320_L	S320	3	195	1.26	176.0	22.94	0.18	0.021	0.62	970	1030	65.6	DTB+LB
T_350_L	S350	3	195	1.54	215.1	28.00	0.22	0.038	0.39	850	970	82.4	DTB+LB
T_550_L	S550	3	195	1.25	174.6	22.78	0.30	0.045	0.88	650	1090	78.4	DTB+LB
T_780_L	DP780	3	195	1.01	141.1	18.42	0.36	0.110	1.07	650	980	63.1	DTB+LB
T_320_D	S320	2	645	1.26	176.0	22.94	0.12	0.679	0.47	3250	1710	55.0	DTB+FB
T_350_D	S350	2	645	1.53	213.7	27.85	0.25	0.977	0.39	1570	1680	70.8	DTB+LB+FB
T_550_D	S550	2	645	1.25	174.6	22.78	0.41	0.026	0.64	1570	2050	65.0	DTB+LB
T_780_D	DP780	2	645	1.01	141.1	18.42	0.37	0.149	0.76	1480	1900	49.0	DTB+LB

¹⁾ Mean value of all test specimens; ²⁾ Definitions acc. to Fig. 8 b); ³⁾ LB=Local Buckling, DTB=Distortional Buckling; FB=Flexural Buckling

Fig. 9. Load-bearing capacity acc. to the compression tests on T-shaped shelf uprights with load application at the center of gravity of the net section a) Ultimate load and utilization of the load-bearing capacity b) Test specimen T_320_1,25_L2 [2] after testing

5 DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A NUMERICAL MODEL

Numerical simulations were used to optimize the cross-section geometry of the shelf uprights. First, a numerical model was developed and validated using the results of the compression tests, see clause 4. For this purpose, a shell model was created using the FE software ANSYS (2020R2) [6]. Both the test specimen and the head plates were generated from Shell181 elements (4 nodes, each with 3 degrees of freedom of displacement and 3 degrees of freedom of rotation), see Fig. 10 a). The nodes between the head plate and the specimen were fused to reproduce the clamping of the test specimen in the grooved head plates. The simple support was generated by the fact that the nodes of the head plates, which were located in the symmetry axis of the T-shaped section, were supported in a non-displaceable manner in the z-direction. The node in the center of gravity of the T-shaped sections was held in the y-direction and supported on the base plate in x-direction. This node was additionally subjected to an axial load on the head plate. Simulations were then carried out in accordance with prEN1993-1-14 [7] using the analysis type GMNIA. For this purpose, a bilinear material model was implemented using the tested material properties (Table 2). In addition, the measured imperfections of the specimen (Table 4) were applied. The imperfection shape corresponding to local buckling with the measured maximum amplitude w_0 was applied as an

eigenmode via a critical buckling analysis. The imperfection shapes corresponding to the distortional buckling and the global precurvatures were applied as a sine half-wave.

Exemplarily, a comparison between the numerical simulations and the experimental tests is shown in *Fig. 10 b*). Overall, the tests could be reproduced with sufficient accuracy using the numerical model. Both the relevant failure mechanisms and the maximum load achieved (mean value of the deviation $m_x=1.075$) showed good agreement.

Fig. 10. a) Numerical model generated using ANSYS (2020R2) b) comparison of the failure modes

6 OPTIMIZATION OF THE SHELF UPRIGHT SECTION

6.1 Generalized numerical model

The aim of the numerical optimization of the shelf upright cross-section made of high-strength steels is to achieve at least the same load-bearing capacity as a conventional shelf upright made of S350GD ($t=1.5$ mm), but to need as less material as possible by using high-strength steels DP780, S550GD or CP980. In addition, the utilization of the high material strength should be optimized.

To standardize the numerical simulations and for direct comparison of the simulation results, a simplified bilinear material model is used. For this purpose, the minimum nominal value of the yield strength $R_{e,min}$ from *Table 2* is used. Furthermore, the recommendations for FE-simulations acc. to EN 1993-1-14 [7] are followed:

- A Young's modulus of 200,000 N/mm² is assumed.
- The combination of local-global imperfections that leads to the lowest load-bearing capacity is applied. Therefore, (I.) global precurvature as a sine half-wave with an amplitude $L/1000$, (II.) an imperfection corresponding to local buckling with the maximum amplitude $b/200$ (b =width of the web) and (III.) an imperfection corresponding to distortional buckling according to *Eq. (1)* are taken into account. The eigenform of a linear-elastic critical buckling analysis was used to implement the imperfection shape corresponding to local buckling and distortional buckling.

$$e_{0,dist} = 0.3 \cdot t \cdot \sqrt{\frac{N_{pl,net}}{N_{cr,d}}} \quad (1)$$

where $N_{cr,d}$ is the critical buckling load for distortional buckling

$N_{pl,net}$ is the maximum load-bearing capacity of the net cross-section

t is the sheet thickness

6.2 Optimization results

As expected and as shown by the results in Chapter 4, the numerical simulations also prove that it is not sufficient to simply adjust the cross-section thickness to exploit the high material strength of the high-strength steels, as the risk of local and distortional buckling increase due to the thinner sheets. The weak points of the T-shaped section (the outstand open cross-sectional parts and the thin-walled web) were therefore improved and optimized by means of parameter studies. The optimization was initially carried out on short uprights ($L=195$ mm). Then, selected cross-sections were also examined for upright lengths of $L=645$ mm and $L=1000$ mm. *Fig. 11 a*) shows the finally

optimized shelf upright cross-section. Grooves were arranged on the web of the section, which significantly reduced the risk of local buckling. The open cross-section was converted to a closed one to avoid distortional buckling. In practice, this could be realized by continuous clinching, a joint folding of the lips or welding. The corresponding cross-section values and load-bearing capacities numerically achieved can be found in *Table 5*.

By modifying the cross-section, it was possible to significantly reduce the sheet thickness using high-strength steels compared to the reference upright while maintaining the same load-bearing capacity, see *Fig. 10 a)* ($L=195$ mm). The high material strength can be satisfactorily utilized.

With increasing component length, however, it became apparent that the load-bearing capacity of the reference upright could no longer be achieved, particularly when using the CP980 ($R_{e,min}=780$ N/mm²). This is due to the risk of global instabilities of the long uprights. The low sheet thickness significantly reduces the resistance to (torsional) flexural buckling of the member. Mathematically, this is expressed by a large slenderness λ_g for global instabilities.

Table 5. Results of numerical cross-section optimization

Section ¹⁾	Material	L [mm]	t [mm]	A_{net} ²⁾ [mm ²]	I_z ³⁾ [mm ⁴]	$N_{pl,net}$ [kN]	λ_g ⁴⁾	N_{FE} [kN]	$N_{FE}/N_{pl,net}$	N_{FE}/N_{Ref} ⁵⁾	$A_{net}/A_{net,350}$ ⁶⁾
T_550_0,90_46_18	S550	195	0.9	127.5	19279	69.84	0.26	58.20	0.83	0.98	0.609
T_550_0,90_46_18	S550	645	0.9	127.5	19279	69.84	0.88	47.84	0.69	0.92	0.609
T_550_0,90_46_18	S550	1000	0.9	127.5	19279	69.84	1.36	31.74	0.45	0.78	0.609
T_780_1,15_46_18	DP780	195	1.15	162.9	24219	71.39	0.24	60.72	0.85	1.02	0.778
T_780_1,15_46_18	DP780	645	1.15	162.9	24219	71.39	0.79	51.68	0.72	1.00	0.778
T_780_1,15_46_18	DP780	1000	1.15	162.9	24219	71.39	1.22	37.78	0.53	0.97	0.778
T_980_0,75_46_18	CP980	195	0.75	106.2	16301	82.54	0.31	59.96	0.73	1.01	0.507
T_980_0,75_46_18	CP980	645	0.75	106.2	16301	82.54	1.04	50.29	0.61	0.97	0.507
T_980_0,75_46_18	CP980	1000	0.75	106.2	16301	82.54	1.60	27.92	0.34	0.61	0.507

¹⁾Section name: T-shaped_Material_Thickness_Width of web_Depth of closed part of sections acc. *Fig. 11 a)*; ²⁾lowest net cross-section; ³⁾Second moment of area; ⁴⁾related slenderness ratio of the flexural buckling, calculated using I_z ;

⁵⁾ Ratio of the numerically achieved ultimate load N_{FE} to the ultimate load N_{ref} of the reference model acc. to *Fig. 6 a)* (S350GD; $t=1.5$ mm; $N_{ref}(L=195)=59.66$ kN; $N_{ref}(L=645)=51.88$ kN; $N_{ref}(L=1000)=38.81$ kN); ⁶⁾ Ratio of the net cross-section A_{net} to the net cross-section of the reference model acc. to *Fig. 6 a)* (S350GD; $t=1.5$ mm, $A_{net,350}=209.48$ mm²)

Fig. 11. a) Optimized cross-section b) Numerically calculated ultimate load and utilization of the load-bearing capacity as a function of the global slenderness - S350: reference model; S550, DP780, CP980: optimized cross-section

Overall, the research project [2] showed that the use of DP780 ($R_{e,min}=440$ N/mm²) resulted in material savings of up to 22.2% for all shelf upright lengths investigated and can be recommended for the use in the racking industry. In contrast, the use of S550GD (39.1% material savings) and CP980 (49.3% material savings) only proved to be effective for short and medium-length shelf uprights. For longer upright lengths, the resistance to global stability phenomena would have to be increased; this could be achieved by using larger sectional dimensions of additional bracing elements. However, this has to be checked in practical applications if it would limit the storage capacity and would therefore have a negative impact on cost-effectiveness.

7 CONCLUSION

As part of the research project [2], the suitability of high-strength steels for the manufacture of shelving racks was initially investigated. In consultation with shelf manufacturers, two high-strength steels (DP780, S550GD) were selected that can be efficiently used for shelf uprights. Demonstrator uprights were manufactured from DP780 ($R_{e,min}=440 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $t=1.0 \text{ mm}$) and S550GD ($R_{e,min}=550 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $t=1.25 \text{ mm}$). The demonstrator uprights and two commercially available configurations of uprights (S350GD: $R_{e,min}=350 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $t=1.5 \text{ mm}$; S320GD: $R_{e,min}=320 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $t=1.25 \text{ mm}$) were then analyzed in compression tests. The compression tests showed that material could be saved by using the high-strength steels while achieving the same load-bearing capacity compared to reference uprights. However, it was also shown that the high material strength could often not be satisfactorily utilized due to the risk of local and distortional buckling of the upright sections. Therefore, a numerical model was developed in ANSYS (2020R2) and validated using the component tests. Parameter studies were carried out to optimize the upright cross-sections when using high-strength steel. Modified cross-sections for T-shaped shelf uprights were developed with greater resistance to local and distortional buckling. Overall, it was found that the use of DP780 in particular can be recommended for the production of shelf uprights. In contrast, the use of S550GD and CP980 can only be recommended for short and medium-length uprights for the shape of upright examined in this paper. In general, the use of high-strength steels enables material saving while maintaining a high load-bearing capacity for shelf uprights in compression. For components with a high global slenderness, however, the use should be checked depending on the upright cross-section and the rack structure. For further information on the tests carried out, the numerical simulations and optimizations reference is made to the fundamental research report [2].

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